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MICROWAVE GENERATED BIONANOCOMPOSITES FOR SOLUBILITY AND DISSOLUTION RATE ENHANCEMENT OF POORLY WATER SOLUBLE DRUG SIMVASTATIN

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ABSTRACT

Fairly soluble drugs in gastrointestinal (GI) media exhibit complete oral absorption, and thus good bioavailability. About 40% of drugs are not soluble in water in practice and therefore are slowly absorbed, which results in insufficient and uneven bioavailability and GI toxicity. Thus, most exigent phase of drug development practice particularly for oral dosage forms is the enhancement of drug solubility and thereby it's oral bioavailability. The objective of present work was to improve solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water soluble drug Simvastatin by Microwave Generated bionanocomposites technique. The nanocomposites prepared using natural polymers (Gum Ghatti, Guar Gum and Gum Acacia) enhances solubility and dissolution rate of drug. Nanocomposites prepared are characterized by DSC, SEM, and XRD which indicates that crystallinity of Simvastatin has been reduced significantly. Solubility study result helped for selection of gum and gave best ratio of drug and polymer. In vitro drug release from prepared immediate release tablet was compared with marketed formulation. Accelerated stability study of optimized batch was performed at 40°C/75% RH and the results suggested that the formulation was stable for three months. Therefore, microwave generated nanocomposites using natural polymer could be successful technique for enhancing the solubility of poorly water soluble Simvastatin. It should be concluded, that the natural polymers having surfactant activity that enhances the solubility and dissolution rate of drug. The optimum ratio of drug to modified natural polymer was found to be 1:3 w/w. This shows higher dissolution as compared to marketed tablet. The selected SD's showed better anti-cholesterol and anti-lipidimic activity compared to plain drug.

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INTRODUCTION

Many of novel discovered drug molecules suffer from very poor water solubility and hence are prone to limited bioavailability. This is one of the major reasons of new drug candidate failing to reach in the market [1]. The solubility of drug becomes especially important in the pharmaceutical field because it often represents a major factor that controls the bioavailability of drug substance. Now a day 40% of drug in the development stage and 60% of drug coming directly from analysis are poorly water soluble [2]. Water solubility is an essential physicochemical property of drug. For a drug molecule to reach the systemic circulation and to exert the therapeutic effect it must be in aqueous solution form [3]. For the drug to be absorbed from the gastrointestinal tracts (GIT), it should be present in solution state in GI fluid, which forms a critical requirement for absorption of poorly water-soluble drugs. Therefore, there is a great interest to develop an efficient, reliable, and economical method to increase the oral bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs.

Drug absorption from the gastrointestinal (GI) tract can be limited by a variety of factors. Poor aqueous solubility and/or poor membrane permeability of the drug molecule is the most important factor governing the drug absorption from the GIT [4]. For an oral dosage form to elicit therapeutic effect, it is required to first dissolve in gastrointestinal fluids before permeating the membranes of the GI tract to reach systemic circulation. Therefore, a drug with poor aqueous solubility will typically exhibit dissolution rate limited absorption as it will not face any problems in permeating the membranes whereas the drug with poor membrane permeability will typically exhibit permeation rate limited absorption even though it shows good aqueous solubility [5]. Hence two areas of pharmaceutical research that focus on improving the oral bioavailability of active agents include enhancing solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water-soluble drugs and enhancing permeability of poorly permeable drugs[6]

Objectives

- To select the cost effective method that will save the money as well as time and help to improve the solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water soluble drug.
- To prepare the bionanocomposites of Simvastatin by using the biodegradable polymer such as acacia gum, ghatti gum and guar gum with the help of microwave oven for enhancement of solubility and dissolution rate.
- Optimizing the ratio of drug to polymer for bionanocomposite that will show good results in solubility and dissolution rate.
- To characterize the drug, polymer, and prepared BNCs by FTIR,DSC,XRD,SEM,TEM
- To formulate bionanocomposite into conventional dosage form such as tablet.

Microwave irradiation technique[7]

Microwave (MW) irradiation technique is one of the novel techniques for improvement of drug solubility the use of microwave irradiation with the help of microwave oven resulting in to the breakage of internal structure of drug particles resulting in to the formation of nanoparticles which ultimately leads to solubility enhancement. Microwave irradiation is effective instrument for generating molecular dispersion. Microwave irradiation is electromagnetic irradiation located between infrared and radio frequency in the range of 0.3-300GHz which corresponds to wavelengths of 1cm to 1 m. Microwave technique achieve rapid and uniform heating in low heat conductivity material because they directly converted into heat inside the material, mostly that material involves polymers hence this mechanism is adopted widely for drug polymer interaction as well as making polymer cross linkage, drying and structural modification of drug crystal by heating effect.

Bionanocomposites[8, 9]

- A physical mixture of drug and Natural or bio carrier in the composite by nanotechnology and their evaluating parameters as drug release profile by *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* and bioavailability in biological system hence termed Bionanocomposites.
- Nanocomposites are a class of materials, which incorporate nano-sized particles in a matrix of other materials.
- Structures having Nano-scale repeat distances between the different phases that make up the material.
- The group consisting of particles of one compound having diameter in nanosize range (1-100nm) dispersed throughout another material. They generally result from addition of nanofiller to the biopolymer matrices.

Methods for formulation of bionanocomposites

1. Solvent intercalation
2. Melt intercalation
3. Hot melt extrusion
4. Solution compounding method
5. In-situ polymerization Chapter.

Microwave-Assisted Synthesis [10]

The electromagnetic irradiation spectrum of Microwave irradiation (0.3–300 GHz) is lies between the IR and radio frequencies with correspond to wavelengths of 1 cm - 1 m. Microwave techniques were useful technique into the pharmaceutical field for various approaches like as tablets, agglomerates, formation of gel beads, nanomatrix, microspheres, film coats, and solid dispersions.

Microwave frequency

Microwave heating refers the use of electromagnetic waves ranges from 0.01m to 1m wavelength of certain frequency to generate heat in the material. These microwaves lie in the region of the electromagnetic spectrum between mm wave and radio wave i.e. between IR and radio wave and they are defined as those waves with wavelengths between 0.01m to 1m, corresponding to frequency of 30GHz to 0.3GHz.

Fig.1: Microwave frequency spectra.

PRINCIPLE

The basic principle behind the heating in microwave oven is due to the interaction of charged particle of the reaction material with electromagnetic wavelength of particular frequency. The phenomena of producing heat by electromagnetic irradiation are either by collision or by conduction, some time by both. All the wave energy changes its polarity from positive to negative with each cycle of the wave. This cause rapid orientation and reorientation of molecule, which cause heating by collision

Microwave induced diffusion (MIND) technique for preparation of bionanocomposites

In this technique the microwave irradiation reaction takes place between the drug and complexing agent (CA) by using the microwave oven. The drug and CA in definite molar ratio are dissolved in a mixture of water and organic solvent in a specified proportion into a round bottom flask. The mixture is reacted for about one to two minutes at 60°C in the microwave oven. After the completion of reaction, sufficient amount of solvent mixture is added to the above reaction mixture residue, uncomplexed free drug and CA. The obtained precipitate is separated by using whatman filter paper and dried in vacuum oven at 40°C for 48 hrs.

Advantages of microwave heating over conventional heating

- Uniform heating occurs throughout the material as opposed to surface and conventional heating process.
- Better and more rapid process control is achieved
- Reduction in unwanted side reaction (reaction quenching).
- Desirable chemical and physical effects are produced.
- In certain cases selective heating occurs which may significantly increase efficiency and decrease operating cost.
- Floor space requirements are decreased.
- High efficiency of heating
- Purity in final product
- Environmental heat loss is saved.

Mechanism Of Microwave Assist Synthesis

Fig.2: Mechanism of Microwave assisted synthesis.

Heating Mechanism

The mixture may be exposed with high frequency electromagnetic waves. The heating starts from the interaction of electric field of the wave and charged particle in the mixture. Two basic principal mechanisms involve in the heating of mixture of drug and carrier.

Dipolar Polarization

Dipolar polarization is a process by which heat is generated between polar molecules. On exposure to the high electromagnetic field of appropriate frequency, polar molecules try to follow the field and orient themselves in phase with the field. The random motion of particles and random interaction generates heat. Microwave radiation has the appropriate frequency (0.3-30 GHz) to oscillate polar particles and enable enough inter-particle interaction.

Interfacial Polarization:

This mechanism is important for system where a dielectric material is not homogenous, but consist of conducting inclusion of one dielectric in other.

Conduction mechanism:

The mechanism generates heat through resistance to an electric current. The oscillating electromagnetic field produces an oscillation of electrons or ions in a conductor, resulting in an electric current. This current faces internal resistance, which heats the conductor.

MATERIAL AND METHOD.

Simvastatin was gifted by cipla pharma. Ltd, gum ghatti ,gum accasia ,guar gum were purchased from modern science Nashik, microcrystline cellulose sodium starch glycolate gifted by VS Intenation Pvt,Ltd.Daman.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

PREPARATION OF PHYSICAL MIXTURE

Physical mixture of drug with polymer Acacia (AC), Guar gum (G_R), Ghatti gum (GG) were prepared by simple blending of drug with gum in the ratio 1:1 to 1:6 .The physical mixture of drug with polymer were denoted by symbol (PHYACSIM), ($PHYG_R$ GSIM),and (PHYGGSIM)

PREPARATION OF BIONANOCOMPOSITES

The bionanocomposites were prepared by homogenous mixing of accurately weighed amount of individual drug with individual polymer. In this case the weight to weight (W/W) ratio of drug to polymer was taken from 1 to 6 keeping amount of mixture constant. To this mixture 5 mL of water was added for each gram of polymer to make homogenous slurry. The fixed amount of slurry 5gm was taken in glass beaker and irradiated with microwave radiation at power 640 (power grill 20 black, ONIDA) with continuous stirring. Bionanocomposites were grounded in mortar and pestle to obtain the size of 80 to 250 μ m. The bionanocomposites of drug with polymer were denoted by symbol BNC G_R GSIM, BNCACSIM, and BNC G_R GSIM.

Fig. 3: Preparation of Bionanocomposites.

RATIO OPTIMIZATION (DRUG: POLYMER) BY SOLUBILITY

BNCs samples equivalent to 30 mg of BNCACSIM, BNC G_R GSIM, BNC G_R GSIM were placed in 10 ml water in Teflon facing screw capped vial and kept at equilibrium for 24 hr on orbital shaking incubator at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 50 rpm. The content of vials were filtered through 0.2 micron filter and analyzed by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 238 nm. As the concentration of polymer increases also increase in the drug solubility. The optimized ratio of was found to be 1:3 w/w BNC's of Ghatti gum (GG)

CHARACTERIZATION

The characterization of BNC's was performed to assess interaction between drug and polymer.

Attenuated total reflectance spectroscopy (ATR)

ATR studies were carried out for characterization of drug and to check the interaction between drug and polymers. ATR studies of pure drugs, and individual drug with individual polymer (GG, AC, G_RG) is carried the wavelength ranged from 400-4000 cm.

Differential Scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DCS studies of pure drug Simvastatin and bionanocomposites of drug with polymer (Ghatti gum) were employed to access what changes had actually made when bionanocomposites were formulated and by what fact these enhances the solubility of drug. The DSC curves were obtained by Differential Scanning Calorimeter at the heating rate of 10°C/ min from 0 to 300° in nitrogen atmosphere.

X-ray diffraction studies (XRD)

XRD studies of drug Simvastatin and nanocomposites of drug with polymer (Ghatti gum) were carried out to investigate the change in crystallinity when drug was mixed with polymer. XRD pattern were recorded using with Cu-ka radiation. The scanning angle ranged from 10° to 50° of 2θ.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy was used to examine external surface morphology. The morphologies and detailed particle structural characterizations of pure drug and bionanocomposites were observed by scanning electron microscope

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The particle size and shape of pure drug crystal dispersed in polymer were analyzed with Transmission electron microscopy. The morphology of the BNCs were obtained by JEOL/JEM 2100 Transmission electron microscope (TEM) (STIC INDIA Cochin)

Size distribution analysis

Bionanocomposites formulation containing accurate dose of drug was diluted with 20ml distilled water and was then mixed gently by inverting the flask. The particle so formed was determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique using zetasizer (Beckman Coulter Delsa™ NanoCommon, Aurangabad).

Drug content analysis

To calculate the amount of drug incorporated into bionanocomposites drug content analysis was performed by dissolving bionanocomposites mixture in 25mL of methanol. The resulting solution was filtered through 0.2μ membrane filter and analyzed by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at wavelength 238 nm for Simvastatin against methanol as a blank

Powder dissolution test

In-vitro powder dissolution test of optimized ratio was performed by using USP XXIV apparatus II (Paddle) method by using 900ml PH 6.8 Phosphate buffer as a dissolution media. Powder that contain accurate dose of drug (or equivalent to 30 mg of simvastatin) was added in the dissolution media maintaining temperature at 37± 0.5°C and rotation speed of paddle at 50 rpm. 10 ml of sample were withdrawn at the interval of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30minute by replacing 10 ml PH 6.8 Phosphate buffer solution in dissolution media. Samples were filtered by 0.5μ membrane filter and analyzed spectrophotometrically at wavelength of 238 nm.

FORMULATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET

Bionanocomposite of drug with Ghatti gum was selected for formulation of immediate release tablet using superdisintegrant. The compositions used for tablet formulation are given in the table. All the components of tablet were passed through sieve no.60 accurately weighed, mixed and compressed into tablet 10mm punch. (RIMEK Tablet compression machine)

Table no.1: Preparation of Immediate Release Tablet of Simvastatin.

No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1.	BNCGGSIM	80	80	80	80
2.	Microcrystalline Cellulose	110	108	110	108
3.	Sodium starch glycolate	6	6	8	8
4.	Magnesium stearate	2	2	2	2
5.	Talc	2	2	2	2

EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET PRECOMPRESSION EVALUATION

Precompression evaluation includes measurement of angle of repose, Carr's index (Compressibility index), and Hausner's ratio of optimized bionanocomposites and formulation mixture.

Angle of repose

Angle of repose was determined by using funnel method. The mixture of bionanocomposites and formulation was poured through the funnel that can be held vertically until the maximum cone height (h) was obtained. Radius of the heap (r) was measured and the angle of repose (θ) was calculated using the formula

Compressibility

Percent compressibility of powder mix was determined by Carr's compressibility index calculated by following formula.

$$\text{Carr's Index \%} = \frac{\text{Tapped bulk density} - \text{Loose bulk density}}{\text{Tapped bulk density}} \times 100$$

Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio indicates the flow property of powder and ratio of tapped density to bulk density of powder

POST COMPRESSION EVALUATION

Post compression evaluation involves the measurement of weight variation, Friability, Disintegration test, Hardness, Drug content analysis all these tests were performed as per the procedure given in the USP 30 (2007)

Weight variation

Weigh individually 20 whole tablets, and calculate the average weight. The requirements are met if the weights of not more than 2 of the tablets differ from the average weight by more than the percentage listed in the accompanying table and no tablet differs in weight by more than double that percentage.

Disintegration test

Place 1 tablet in each of the tubes of the basket. Operate the apparatus, using water or the specified medium as the immersion fluid, maintained at 37 ± 2 . At the end of 30 minutes, lift the basket from the fluid, and observe the tablets: all of the tablets disintegrate completely. If 1 or 2 tablets fail to disintegrate completely, repeat the test on 12 additional tablets. The requirement is met if not less than 16 of the total of 18 tablets tested disintegrate completely.

Hardness

Hardness of the tablet formulation was determined by Pfizer tester. The tablet was placed vertical between two ends of tester and force is applied. Hardness should be optimum, increase in hardness causes disintegration problem while decrease in hardness causes breakage of tablet during transportation and handling.

Friability

The 10 tablets were accurately weighed and placed in drum (Roche friabilitor). Drum was rotated at the speed of 25 rpm for 4 min. After the rotation tablets were removed and reweighed, and % friability was determined as per the formula.

In vitro dissolution test

In vitro dissolution test was performed according to USP XXIV apparatus 2 (paddle) methods. 900 mL of phosphate buffer 6.8 was used as dissolution media. Tablets of various batches were added to the dissolution media maintaining the temperature $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and rotation speed of paddle at 50 rpm. 10 ml aliquots were withdrawn at 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60 minutes time intervals. The volume was maintained by adding 10 ml of fresh dissolution medium. Samples were filtered through 0.2 micron filter and analyzed spectrophotometrically at wavelength of 238 nm.

Drug content analysis

Drug content analysis was performed to calculate the amount of drug incorporated into the tablet. Simvastatin from powdered tablet was extracted by dissolving them in 25 mL methanol. Simvastatin content in methanolic extract was filtered and analyzed by UV visible spectrophotometer at wavelength 238nm against methanol as a blank.

STABILITY STUDY

Accelerated stability study is carried out as per ICH guidelines. The sample was placed for 3 months in stability chamber at $40^\circ\text{C}/75\% \text{RH}$. Various parameters such as disintegration time, drug content and in-vitro drug release were measured after 0, 30, 60, and 90 days of stability

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Solubility studies

Solubility study is carried out for ratio optimization between the polymer and drug. The ratio having best solubility result is selected for the formulation. Results obtained are on the basis of solubility studies carried out on physical mixture of drug and polymer and their bionanocomposites. The solubility of simvastatin in water was found to be 0.031mg/ml (31.94 μ g/ml).

Table no. 2 Solubility study of Physical mixture.

Drug polymer ratio	PHYGGSIM μ g/ml	PHYACSIM μ g/ml	PHYG _R GSIM μ g/ml
1:1	61.05 \pm 0.51	42.52 \pm 0.34	37.68 \pm 0.07
1:2	128.42 \pm 0.86	50.89 \pm 0.69	43.84 \pm 0.57
1:3	161.05 \pm 0.77	162.10 \pm 0.54	47.36 \pm 0.60
1:4	154.73 \pm 0.54	107.89 \pm 0.28	104.21 \pm 0.25
1:5	154.73 \pm 0.36	149.47 \pm 1.30	163.68 \pm 0.19
1:6	163.15 \pm 0.14	73.15 \pm 0.81	98.94 \pm 0.61

Table no. 3: Solubility study of Bionanocomposites.

Drug polymer ratio	BNCGGSIM μ g/ml	BNCACSIM μ g/ml	BNCG _R GSIM μ g/ml
1:1	214.73 \pm 0.42	66.31 \pm 0.51	56.63 \pm 0.73
1:2	332.63 \pm 0.31	100.52 \pm 0.08	95.78 \pm 0.8
1:3	482.10 \pm 0.64	206.84 \pm 0.38	105.26 \pm 0.12
1:4	425.26 \pm 0.32	293.15 \pm 1.69	201.05 \pm 0.02
1:5	282.63 \pm 0.51	216.84 \pm 0.03	165.26 \pm 0.16
1:6	261.05 \pm 0.26	213.68 \pm 0.6	164.73 \pm 0.20

Powder dissolution study of Bionanocomposite.

Fig.no. 4: Dissolution study of Bionanocomposites.

Drug content analysis of Bionanocomposites

Table no. 4 Drug Content of Bionanocomposites.

Bionanocomposite	BNCGGSIM	BNCACSIM	BNCG _R GSIM
Drug incorporated	95%	93%	92%

DSC Studies

Fig.no. 5: DSC Graphs of pure Simvastatin.

Fig no.6: DSC Graphs of BNCGGSIM.

5. X-Ray diffraction studies

Fig.no.7: XRD pattern of pure simvastatin.

Fig. no.8: XRD pattern of BNCGGSIM.

Scanning Electron microscopy (SEM)

Fig. no.9: SEM images of pure drug.

Fig.no10: SEM images of BNCGGSIM.

Particle size Analysis

Fig. no.11: Particle Size Analysis.

PRE COMPRESSION EVALUATION

Table no. 5 : Precompression Evaluation.

Sr. No	Formulation	Angle of repose	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
1	F1	31.79 ± 1.64	10.61 ± 0.41	1.132 ± 0.017
2	F2	30.54 ± 1.72	11.78 ± 1.92	1.132 ± 0.007
3	F3	30.32 ± 1.47	10.35 ± 1.03	1.115 ± 0.020
4	F4	30.24 ± 2.24	11.70 ± 1.30	1.126 ± 0.012
5	Pure	37.41 ± 1.70	15.28 ± 1.21	1.180 ± 0.017

POST COMPRESSION EVALUATION.

Table no. 6: Postcompression Evaluation.

Sr. No	Formulation	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness(Kg/cm ²)	% friability	Drug content uniformity (%)	Disintegration time (S)
1.	F1	202.0± 1.48	3.23 ± 0.18	0.78%	98.39	61 ± 1.66
2.	F2	201.3 ± 1.92	3.56 ± 0.13	0.63%	100.95	56 ± 2.18
3.	F3	203.4 ± 1.21	2.92 ± 0.23	0.59%	98.52	44 ± 2.06
4.	F4	203.7± 1.52	3.62 ± 0.16	0.61%	97.50	46 ± 2.33

In - vitro dissolution study of tablets

Table no. 7: In-vitro dissolution study of tablets.

Sr.No	Time (Min)	Marketed preparation	F1 (%DR)	F2 (%DR)	F3 (%DR)	F4 (%DR)
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	5	22.88 ± 0.79	31.89± 1.3	31.29 ± 0.64	30.25 ± 0.84	27.56± 2.20
3	10	32.16 ± 0.64	38.61± 0.89	33.83 ± 2.2	39.35 ± 1.2	27.56± 2.20
4	15	43.77± 1.3	42.79 ± 2.1	43.68± 0.35	42.49± 1.64	45.32 ± 0.73
5	20	62.32 ± 0.98	53.68± 1.1	60.55± 1.4	63.23± 0.66	58.16± 1.1
6	25	72.50± 1.4	79.50± 1.89	79.65 ± 0.64	81.14 ± 1.34	81± 1.45
7	30	76.62 ± 0.71	90.40± 1.71	89.05± 1.3	91 ± 0.49	82.26± 1.78

Fig.no.12: *In-vitro* dissolution tests of Simvastatin tablets.

From the result of preformulation and post formulation study it can be observed that the formulation F3 of simvastatin shows best result and they are optimized.

Stability studies.

Optimized formulation was subjected to stability studies. Various parameters such as disintegration time, drug content and in-vitro drug release were measured after 0, 30, 60, and 90 days of stability. Result of stability study shows, there is no significant change in disintegration time, drug content and in-vitro drug release after stress condition during stability study. From stability study it can be conclude that prepared formulation is stable and not much affected by stress condition

Table no. 8: Stability study.

Time (Days)	Disintegration time (sec)	% Drug content	% In-vitro drug Release
0	44 ± 1.42	98.37	91.49± 1.17
30	43 ± 1.08	98.81	90.24± 1.24
60	44 ± 0.22	97.59	90.19 ± 1.56
90	44 ± 1.62	98.12	90 ± 1.36

CONCLUSION

Simvastatin is first choice of drug for treating all types of severe hyperlipidemia, but these benefits are less enjoyed due to its limited solubility. The natural polymers having surfactant activity that enhances the solubility and dissolution rate of drug can be used, but due to high viscosity many of these polymers also having limitation as carriers for dissolution enhancement this problem is overcome by reducing the viscosity of polymers. This natural polymers having advantage over other synthetic polymer as this polymers are biocompatible, biodegradable and having low cost. On heating of the natural polymers (GG) at particular time and temperature condition it reduces the viscosity and changes the surface property which is useful to polymers for use as drug carrier for dissolution enhancement. Modified natural polymer gum ghatti have great potential for enhancement of solubility, dissolution rate and thereby bioavailability of poorly soluble Simvastatin. The SD's of Simvastatin with polymer enhances the solubility by converting it into amorphous form, reducing the particle size and increasing the wettability. The optimum ratio of drug to modified natural polymer was found to be 1:3 w/w. This shows higher dissolution as compared to marketed tablet. The selected SD's showed better anti-cholesterol and anti-lipidemic activity compared to plain drug.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

PHYGGSIM	Physical mixture of Simvastatin with Gum Ghatti	BNCGRGSIM	Bionanocomposites of Simvastatin with Guar gum
PHYGRGSIM	Physical mixture of Simvastatin with Guar Gum	BNCGGSIM	Bionanocomposites of Simvastatin with Gum Ghatti
PHYACSIM	Physical mixture of Simvastatin with Acacia	BNCACSIM	Bionanocomposites of Simvastatin with Acacia
XRD	X- ray diffraction	DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
mm	Millimeter	ATR	Attenuated Total Reflectance
Cm	Centimeter	AC	Acacia
BNC	Bionanocomposites	GG	Gum Ghatti
MW	Microwave	GRG	Guar Gum

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